

LEVEL OF ICT COMPETENCIES OF BASIC EDUCATION TEACHERS IN KATANGAWAN DISTRICT: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Level of ICT Competencies of Basic Education Teachers in Katangawan District: A Cross-Sectional Study

Rossana L. Salanio,* Geraldine D. Rodriguez
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study assessed the ICT competencies of 216 basic education teachers from Katangawan District Schools. The variables of the study were the level of ICT competencies of the respondent-teachers and the intervention program. Frequency count, percentage, rank, and weighted mean were used in analyzing the gathered data.. The existing ICT competency programs of schools were well-equipped with the necessary infrastructure, productivity tools, internet connectivity, and relevant training conducted. Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the teachers of the different schools in Katangawan District Schools perceived themselves to be moderately but sufficiently ICT competent. The researcher recommended periodical conduct of training and workshops and conduct of competency testing and assessment of ICT competencies between and among the schools in Katangawan District. This study promotes effective integration of technology in education for improved student learning outcomes.

Keywords: *educational management, ICT competence, teachers' ICT skills, cross sectional study*

Introduction

The combination of technology in education aspires to help students cope with the fast-changing world that depends on facts, systems, and information technology. Technology can offer creative solutions allowing learners to access information and knowledge, participate fully in society, and engage in high-quality lifelong learning opportunities. Digital citizenship - the ability and ethical values to participate in society online – is an increasingly vital element in the 21st Century. The effective integration of information and communications technology in schools and classrooms can transform pedagogy and empower students. This means that schools must take concrete actions to integrate ICT into classroom learning activities. Further, ICT use in the classroom gives students opportunities to learn and apply the required 21st-century skills (Ghavifekr et al., 2016; UNESCO, 2018).

Furthermore, Information and Communication Technology, or ICT, is a revolutionary development in the Philippine educational system. It opens a wide variety of opportunities both for teachers and students. Transferring information, collecting statistics, and researching are the benefits people can get from ICT services. However, most teachers need to be ICT knowledgeable, if not this results in poor student and school performance. Technology has given society many choices, making limited resources accessible. Despite the growing popularity of ICT tools, many educators still struggle to add new ICT tools to their lesson plans (Lorenzo, 2016; Nikolopoulou & Gialamas, 2016).

In the Philippines, several policies that were needed to help integrate ICT into education were made public, including increased teacher training, the supply of computer infrastructures, and the strategic integration of ICT into the curriculum. Strong leadership of teachers in the Philippines benefited from a variety of training providers that offered "professional development in a range of subject areas using different methods, but it is at the discretion of the training provider to design the content, quality, and duration of the training would be (Tomaro, 2018; Sasing, 2020).

In addition, in these times when there is a new normal for instructional delivery as a result of the world pandemic, it becomes all the more imperative that teachers are equipped with the necessary ICT competence to ensure that the learning experience remains meaningful not only for the students but for all the stakeholders as well. Therefore, teachers need to be trained in the pedagogical use of ICTs to use the available school infrastructure for effective teaching effectively (Chiinza et al., 2020).

In the context of Katangawan district, teachers are highly encouraged to use ICT in teaching and this were rated during the conduct of classroom observations. The schools were providing initiatives to provide relevant training and workshops to the teachers. However, there are still those teachers who are not used to integrating technology in teaching. Thus, this study assessed the ICT competencies of teachers in Katangawan District Schools in General Santos City.

Research Questions

It specifically looked for responses to the following queries:

1. What is the ICT competency level of the respondents in the areas of?
 - 1.1. technology operations and concepts;
 - 1.2. social and ethical standards;
 - 1.3. pedagogical standards; and
 - 1.4. professional standards
2. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention program can be formulated?

Methodology

The methods and processes used to collect the study's data are described in this chapter. It consists of the research design, respondents, locale of the study, sampling techniques, instrument, data gathering procedures, and analysis methods.

This study employed the cross-sectional survey research method. Thomas (2020) defined a cross-sectional survey as a research design where data from many individuals are collected simultaneously. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the outcome of this research. The cross-sectional survey was appropriate since this study gathered responses from different teacher-respondents in different Katangawan District Schools. Their responses were gathered in a one-time frame, and the researcher did not influence the observed variables of the study.

The study was conducted in all schools of Katangawan District, specifically Katangawan Central Elementary School, JR Lansang Elementary School, Datu Dumagkal Danial Elementary School, Batomelong Elementary School, OT Santos Elementary School, Daan Banwang Elementary School, Upper Labay Elementary School, Datu Andiam Manza National High School, Upper Labay High School, Samboang Ngilay High School, and Florence M. Santos High School. All these schools are located within General Santos City. The Katangawan District was chosen since a significant number of the schools in this district were located in remote rural areas where the existence of a digital divide is more likely since, in developing countries like the Philippines, a digital divide can exist even in the smallest political unit of the country (Cimene, 2019).

According to DepEd Gensan, there were 216 teachers from the eleven schools included in the Katangawan District Schools in 2020. Only permanent teachers were included in the survey. For the study on the level of ICT competencies of teachers in Katangawan District, participants were selected based on specific inclusion criteria. Firstly, the teachers needed to be currently employed in Katangawan District schools, ensuring their relevance to the local context. Secondly, they should have a minimum of two years of teaching experience, ensuring a certain level of professional familiarity with instructional practices. Lastly, participants were required to have received some form of ICT training or professional development to assess their existing ICT competencies accurately.

To ensure the study's focus on teachers with a sufficient level of experience and exposure to ICT, certain exclusion criteria were established. Firstly, teachers with less than two years of teaching experience were excluded from participation to prioritize those with more extensive professional backgrounds. Secondly, educators who had not received any form of ICT training or professional development were excluded to ensure that the study primarily assessed teachers' existing ICT competencies rather than their potential for growth in this area. Lastly, teachers who were not currently employed in Katangawan District schools were excluded to maintain the study's localized scope.

In the event that a participant's circumstances changed during the study, withdrawal criteria were established to ensure the integrity and reliability of the research. If a teacher withdrew voluntarily or due to unforeseen circumstances, their data would be excluded from the final analysis to maintain the integrity of the study's findings. Withdrawal criteria also included instances where participants did not meet the inclusion criteria after enrollment or failed to adhere to the study's guidelines and protocols, ensuring that the remaining data accurately represented the target population in the Katangawan District study.

The researcher obtained a list of all schools in the Katangawan District. The teachers were categorized according to employment status from this list: "permanent" and "job order." The survey did not include the teachers in "job order" status. After categorizing the respondents and then identifying the permanent teachers, complete enumeration was used. According to Arnab (2017), complete enumeration eliminates sampling error, although the method also does not guarantee exact results.

In the data collection, the researcher adopted the contents of the National ICT Competencies Standard for Teachers and added the profile and existing ICT competency program of the Katangawan District Schools. The teacher modified the questionnaires to ensure that they fit the context of the locale. It has undergone validation process. The tool was comprised of only one part that measured the competency level of teachers based on their perception using parameters from the National ICT Standards.

The researcher obtained permission from the District Supervisor of Katangawan District and principals and administrators of the participant schools to conduct the survey. The researcher handled the distribution of the questionnaires. The survey was administered in face-to-face modality. An official letter was copy furnished for the respondents. Furthermore, the researcher asked for the respondents' consent before administering the instruments. The study manuscript underwent an Ethics Review to ensure adherence to the ethical principles in conducting the research. The researcher personally administered the research questionnaire to the respondents. The instruments were retrieved right after the respondents were done answering.

The researcher used appropriate statistical tools to analyze and interpret the data gathered in this study. The frequency count was used to determine teacher-respondents in Katangawan District schools. Percentage and weighted mean were used to determine the ICT competency level of Katangawan District teachers in terms of Technology Operation and Concepts, Social and Ethical, Pedagogical, and Professional

Results and Discussion

Level of ICT Competency of Teachers in Katangawan District Schools

This study determined the level of ICT competency of the teachers in Katangawan District in terms of technology operation and concepts measured as follows: (1) Standard 1 - demonstrate knowledge and skills in basic computer and other information devices, including basic troubleshooting and maintenance; (2) Standard 2 - use appropriate office and teaching productivity tools; (3) Standard 3 - understand and effectively use the internet and network application and resources; and (4) Standard 4 - demonstrate knowledge and skills in information and data management.

For social and ethical: (1) Standard 1 – comprehend and abide by the legal requirements in using technology; (2) Standard 2 - recognize and practice ethical use of technology at both personal and professional levels; (3) Standard 3 - can plan, model and promote a safe and sound technology-supported learning environment; considers social and cultural diversity, as well as learning.

Regarding the pedagogical indicators: Standard 1 - apply technology to develop students higher order thinking skills and creativity; (2) Standard 2 - give students performance tasks that allow them to find and evaluate information, as well as to effectively communicate; and (3) Standard 3 - create open, adaptable learning environments that make use of technology to facilitate a range of student interactions, cooperative learning, and peer education).

In terms of professional competency: (1) Standard 1 - proactively engage in exploring and learning new and emerging technologies; (2) Standard 2 - continually assess and consider how well the field is using technology Indicators; and (3) Standard 3 - cooperate with peers and stakeholders to advance the use of technology in education and beyond by exchanging experiences and knowledge. In analyzing the data, the mean was applied.

It is shown in Table 1 that based on their responses, the teachers perceived that they were highly competent in terms of identifying and defining the functions of the main components such as the monitor, CPU, keyboard, and mouse) of the computer (4.10); identifying and defining the functions of the computer peripherals, i.e., printer, scanner, modem, digital, camera, speaker, etc. (3.96); organizing and managing computer files, folders, and directories (3.67); using the storage devices, i.e., hard disk, diskette, CD, flash memory, etc. (3.63); and understanding the basic functions of the operation (3.44).

On the other hand, they thought that they were "only" competent in matters pertaining to connecting the main component, configuring peripherals and installing drivers when required (3.31); configuring computer settings of various software and hardware (3.12), protecting the computer from virus, spyware, adware, malware, hackers, etc. (3.08), and in using online and offline help facilities for troubleshooting, maintenance, and update of applications (3.03).

Based on their overall assessment, the teachers believed they were highly competent in demonstrating knowledge and skills in basic computer and other information devices, including basic troubleshooting and maintenance.

Table 1. Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Technology Operation and Concepts (Standard 1)

<i>Standard 1: Demonstrate knowledge and skills in basic computer and other information devices, including basic troubleshooting and maintenance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can identify and define the functions of the main components (i. e. monitor, CPU, keyboard, mouse) of the computer.	4.10	Agree	Highly Competent
I can identify and define the functions of the computer peripherals (i.e. printer, scanner, modem, digital, camera, speaker, etc.).	3.96	Agree	Highly Competent
I can organize and manage computer files, folders, and directories.	3.67	Agree	Highly Competent
I can use storage devices (i.e. hard disk, diskette, CD, flash memory, et.).	3.63	Agree	Highly Competent
I can understand the basic functions of the operation.	3.44	Agree	Highly Competent
I can properly connect main component, configure peripherals and install drivers when required.	3.31	Neutral	Competent
I can configure computer settings of various software and hardware.	3.12	Neutral	Competent
I can protect the computer from virus, spyware adware, malware, hackers, etc.	3.08	Neutral	Competent
I can use online and offline help facilities for troubleshooting, maintenance and update of applications.	3.03	Neutral	Competent
Overall Mean	3.48	Agree	Highly Competent

Having competency in basic computer operation and manipulation meant that the teachers were able to open the computer units by plugging them into the right energy source, pressing the "power on" button, performing at least basic manipulation, pinpointing the functions of at least the built-in software, identify or describe the functions of other hardware, and understand the functions of the main operating system.

Meyers, Erickson, and Small (2013) contended that concerns about the lack of digital access had given way to concerns about being digitally illiterate, i.e., lacking the skills, understanding, and practices required to successfully navigate the ever-changing digital landscape. Jones (2004) found that a very significant determinant of the teachers' levels of participation in ICT is their level of reliance on using the technology. Teachers who have little or no confidence in using computers in their work will try to avoid them altogether, and teachers who have more confidence in their computer skills are likely to use the technology more (Meyers, Erickson & Small,

2013).

It is shown in Table 2 that the teachers perceived that they were highly competent in terms of using a word processor to enter and edit texts and images (3.87), formatting text, control margins, layout, and tables (3.97), printing, storing and retrieving text documents from a word processor (3.94), using a calculation spreadsheet to enter data, sort data and format cells into tables (3.68), making computations, using formula and creating graphs using spreadsheets (3.53), printing and storing data tables using a spreadsheet application (3.63), using a presentation package to add text and sequence a presentation (3.63), enhancing slide presentations by adding sound, customizing animation and inserting images (3.51), printing presentation hand-outs and storing slide presentations (3.75), making effective class presentations using the slides and LCD projector (3.71), obtaining digital photos and other media from CDs, flash drives, websites, etc. (3.1), and cropping, scaling, color correcting and enhancing digital images (3.56).

On the other hand, they thought that they were "only" competent in matters pertaining to playing various media files using appropriate players (3.37), stitching together video footage and soundtracks and simple enhancements – transitions, titles, etc. (3.07), connecting and setting up scanners, cameras, and mobile devices to capture digital photos (3.20), and utilizing internet repositories and optical media (CD, DVD, and flash drive) for the storage of digital photographs (3.19).

Based on their overall assessment, the teachers believed they were highly competent in using appropriate office and teaching productivity tools. Hence, being able to use appropriate office and teaching productivity tools enabled the teachers to enhance and make their learning materials and presentations even more interesting for the students.

Productivity software has the potential to significantly minimize the amount of time teachers spend on repetitive and tedious tasks. Furthermore, productivity software can be integrated into the curriculum and impact the learning of all students (Gunter & Thomson, 2011).

Education professionals can better support students digitally by staying on top of their game with the aid of productivity tools (Athuraliya, 2021).

Table 2. Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Technology Operation and Concepts (Standard 2)

<i>Standard 2: Use appropriate office and teaching productivity tools</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can use a word processor to enter and edit texts and images.	3.87	Agree	Highly competent
I can format text, control margins, layout and tables.	3.97	Agree	Highly competent
I can print, store and retrieve text documents from a word processor.	3.94	Agree	Highly competent
I can use a calculation spreadsheet to enter data, sort data and format cells into tables.	3.68	Agree	Highly competent
I can make computations, use formula and create graphs using spreadsheets.	3.53	Agree	Highly competent
I can print and store data tables using a spreadsheet application.	3.63	Agree	Highly competent
I can use a presentation package to add text and sequence a presentation.	3.63	Agree	Highly competent
I can enhance slide presentations by adding sound, customizing animation and inserting images.	3.51	Agree	Highly competent
I can print presentation hand-outs and store slide presentations.	3.75	Agree	Highly competent
I can make effective class presentations using the slides and LCD projector.	3.71	Agree	Highly competent
I can acquire digital images and other media from web sites, CD, flash drives, etc.	3.71	Agree	Highly competent
I can crop, scale, color correct and enhance digital images.	3.56	Agree	Highly competent
I can play various media files using appropriate players.	3.37	Neutral	Competent
I can stitch together video footages and soundtracks and simple enhancements – transitions, titles, etc.	3.07	Neutral	Competent
I can attach and configure scanners, cameras, cell phones to acquire digital images.	3.20	Neutral	Competent
I can store digital images using optical media (CD, DVD, flash disk) and online repositories.	3.19	Neutral	Competent
Overall Mean	3.58	Agree	Highly Competent

It is shown in Table 3 that the teachers perceived that they were competent in terms of connecting to the internet via dial-up or LAN (3.28), configuring and using Web browsers and help applications (3.23), sending and receiving emails with attachments, managing emails and use LAN and Web-based mail servers (3.42), using voice, teleconferencing, and synchronous and asynchronous web-based communication technologies like instant messengers effectively (3.30), connecting and using shared printers, shared folders and other devices within a network (3.26), using search engines, web directories, and bookmarks effectively (3.26), and downloading and installing the necessary software, such as shareware, freeware, updates, patches, viewers, and support software (3.21).

Based on the overall mean of 3.28, it was clear that the teachers were competent in terms of understanding and using the internet and network applications and resources effectively.

Teachers use ICT to make the teaching-learning process easy and interesting. A competent teacher has several skills and techniques for providing successful teaching. So, the development and increase of skills and competencies of teachers require knowledge of ICT and Science & Technology. In modern science and technological societies, education demands more knowledge from the teacher

regarding ICT and skills to use ICT in the teaching-learning process. The knowledge of ICT is also required for a pre-service teacher during their training program because this integrated technological knowledge helps a prospective teacher to know the world of technology in a better way by which it can be applied in the future for the betterment of the students (Bhattacharjee & Deb, 2016).

Table 3. *Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Technology Operation and Concepts (Standard 3)*

<i>Standard 3: Understand and effectively use the Internet and network application and resources</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can connect to the internet via dial-up or LAN.	3.28	Neutral	Competent
I can configure and use Web browsers and help applications.	3.23	Neutral	Competent
I can send and receive emails with attachments, manage emails and use LAN and Web-based mail servers.	3.42	Agree	Highly Competent
I can effectively use synchronous and asynchronous Web-based communication tools like instant messengers, voice and teleconferencing.	3.30	Neutral	Competent
I can connect and use shared printers, shared folders and other devices within a network.	3.26	Neutral	Competent
I can effectively use search engines, web directories, and bookmarks.	3.26	Neutral	Competent
I can download and install relevant applications including freeware, shareware, updates, patches, viewers, and support applications.	3.21	Neutral	Competent
Overall	3.28	Neutral	Competent

It is shown in Table 4 that the teachers perceived that they were highly competent in distributing, sharing, publishing, and printing information via print or the web (3.66). On the other hand, they believed that they were competent enough in properly acknowledging information sources – online and offline (3.30), searching and gathering data from both online and offline sources, including text and non-text (3.28), efficiently storing and organizing collected information using directories, drives or databases (3.20), and in using search engines, directories, crawlers, and agents to locate information sources effectively (3.13).

Based on the overall mean of 3.31, it was clear that the teachers thought they were competent in terms of demonstrating knowledge and skills in information and data management.

In order to support teachers' diagnostic pedagogical ability to use data and evidence to improve the quality of teaching and identify the best ways in which teaching performance can be enhanced, a new theoretical approach called "Teaching Analytics" (TA) has been developed. It combines teaching expertise, visual analytics, and design-based research. It provides a platform for teachers to use data to reflect on teaching outcomes which can be used to engage teachers in a meaningful dialogue to improve the quality of teaching. However, teachers need to develop their teacher data literacy and data inquiry skills to learn about teaching challenges teachers need to equip themselves with the knowledge necessary to understand the complexity of teaching and the learning environment. Providing teachers access to analytics associated with their teaching practice and learning outcome can improve the quality of teaching practice (Ndukwe & Daniel, 2020).

Table 4. *Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Technology Operation and Concepts (Standard 4)*

<i>Standard 4: Demonstrate knowledge and skills in information and data management</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can distribute, share, publish and print information via print or web.	3.66	Agree	Highly competent
I can properly acknowledge information sources- online and offline.	3.30	Neutral	Competent
I can search and collect textual and non-textual information from online and offline sources.	3.28	Neutral	Competent
I can efficiently store and organize collected information using directories, drives or databases.	3.20	Neutral	Competent
I can effectively use search engines, directories, crawlers and agents to locate information sources.	3.13	Neutral	Competent
Overall	3.31	Neutral	Competent

It is shown in Table 5 that the teachers perceived that they were competent when it came to an understanding the legal implications of software licenses and fair use (3.30), understanding and explaining the basic concepts of Intellectual property rights (3.35), and differentiating and identifying the copyright, trademark, and patent of various products (3.21).

Based on the overall mean of 3.29, it was clear that the teachers thought they were competent in terms of understanding and observing legal practices in the use of technology.

Long before kids are taught how to respond ethically to real-life circumstances, technology puts ethical dilemmas to the fore. McGilvery (2011) emphasized that "teachers must practice appropriate and professional behavior while actively engaging students in authentic learning experiences using blogs, wiki spaces, learning management systems, online research, and much more. They must demonstrate, guide, and help students practice appropriate and professional behavior.

Table 5. *Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Social and Ethical (Standard 1)*

<i>Standard 1: Understand and observe legal practices in the use of technology</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can understand the legal implications of software licenses and fair use.	3.30	Neutral	Competent
I can understand and explain the basic concepts of Intellectual property rights.	3.35	Neutral	Competent
I can differentiate and identify the copyright, trademark, patent of various products.	3.21	Neutral	Competent
Overall Mean	3.29	Neutral	Competent

It is shown in Table 6 that the teachers perceived that they were highly competent when it came to showing considering the privacy and cyber etiquette, phone etiquette, and similar utilization of technology (3.86) and advocating the responsible usage of different technologies like computers, cell phones, etc. (3.66). However, the instructors thought that they were only capable of advocating against piracy for all IPR-related products, such as software, data, music, and movies. (3.49), in acknowledging sources used in their own work (3.34), and in detecting plagiarism in the student's work (3.27).

Their overall assessment, based on an overall mean of 3.52, however, indicated that they perceived themselves as highly competent in recognizing and practicing ethical use of technology at both personal and professional levels.

Table 6. *Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Social and Ethical (Standard 2)*

<i>Standard 2: Recognize and practice ethical use of technology in both personal and professional levels</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can show respect for privacy and cyber etiquette, phone etiquette, and similar use of technology.	3.86	Agree	Highly competent
I can advocate the responsible use of various technologies like computers, cell phones, etc.	3.66	Agree	Highly competent
I can be an Anti-Piracy advocate for all products with IPR like music, data, video and software.	3.49	Neutral	Competent
I can properly acknowledge sources used in own work.	3.34	Neutral	Competent
I can detect plagiarism in the student's work.	3.27	Neutral	Competent
Overall Mean	3.52	Agree	Highly competent

Organizations and professions should create explicit internal rules, procedures, standards, and best practices that are specially tailored to their unique activities and issues because no one code of technology ethics can apply to all situations and practitioners. This code of technology ethics should be sincerely implemented in the respective schools among their respective personnel (Vallor, 2018).

It is shown in Table 7 that the teachers believed that they were highly competent in demonstrating how to properly handle computer devices and the proper use of applications (3.63) in monitoring how students utilize the computer, specifically on software, hardware, computer games, and internet activities (3.42), in maintaining a clean and orderly learning environment for students (3.78) and promoting and implementing rules and regulations on the proper use of computers (3.76). However, in reporting malfunctions and problems with computer software and hardware accurately, they indicated that they were competent enough (3.40).

Their overall assessment, based on an overall mean of 3.60, however, indicated that they perceived themselves as highly competent in planning, modeling, and promoting a safe and sound technology-supported learning environment.

The use of ICT by teachers who are digitally literate and trained can help students develop higher-order thinking skills, offer them unique and creative ways to express what they have learned, and better prepare them to deal with the rapid technological change that is occurring in both society and the workplace (Buckingham, 2005).

The teacher is one of the key players in promoting successful TSIL environments. The first step is for teachers to develop an understanding of the fundamentals of TSIL, as well as the ability to transfer their understanding into practical applications of web-based technologies (Hakverdi-Can & Duygu Sönmez, 2012).

Table 7. *Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Social and Ethical (Standard 3)*

<i>Standard 3: Plan, model and promote a safe and sound technology-supported learning environment</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I can demonstrate proper handling of computer devices and use of applications.	3.63	Agree	Highly competent
I can monitor how students use the computer specifically on software, hardware, computer games, and internet activities.	3.42	Neutral	Competent
I can maintain a clean and orderly learning environment for students.	3.78	Agree	Highly competent
I can promote and implement rules and regulations on properly using computers.	3.76	Agree	Highly competent
I can accurately report malfunctions and problems with computer software and hardware.	3.40	Neutral	Competent
Overall Mean	3.60	Agree	Highly competent

It is shown in Table 8 that the teachers believed that they were highly competent in preparing lessons and activities appropriate to the level of learning and cultural background of students (3.59). However, in the areas of designing class activities to minimize the effects

on students being disadvantaged or left out, helping minimize the effects of the digital divide by giving access to digital materials for all students, and adapting activities utilizing specialized software and hardware for physically disadvantaged students, they considered themselves competent with mean scores 3.47, 3.41, and 3.40, respectively.

Their overall assessment, based on an overall mean of 3.47, indicated that they perceived themselves as competent in facilitating equitable access to technology that addressed learning and social and cultural diversity.

Research and various studies have shown that using multimedia in the classroom increases creativity and innovative problem-solving and improves communication between people. Technology helps students who

have access and equity difficulties. With the use of technology, educators can improve their methods of instruction and student learning while also being more accommodating to different learning styles. In addition to fostering student learning and self-esteem, this use of technology will enable educators to push past their conventional limitations. Creativity and imagination are made possible by technology and the internet (Hollenbeck & Hollenbeck, 2009).

Table 8. Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Social and Ethical (Standard 4)

<i>Standard 4: Facilitate equitable access to technology that addresses learning, social and cultural diversity</i>	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I can prepare lessons and activities appropriate to the level of learning and cultural background of students.	3.59	Agree	Highly competent
I can design class activities to minimize the effects on students being disadvantaged or left-out.	3.47	Neutral	Competent
I can help minimize the effects of the digital divide by providing access to digital materials for all students.	3.41	Neutral	Competent
I can adapt activities using specialized hardware and software for physically disadvantaged students.	3.40	Neutral	Competent
Overall Mean	3.47	Neutral	Competent

It is shown in Table 9 that the respondents perceived themselves as sufficiently competent in making students use databases, spreadsheets, concept mapping tools, communication tools, etc. (3.15) and in encouraging them to do data analysis, problem-solving, decision-making, and exchange of ideas (3.28).

Their overall mean of 3.22 indicated that they considered themselves competent in applying technology to develop students' higher-order thinking skills and creativity.

Before entering the real world, students must acquire crucial higher-order thinking skills. Students must learn to analyze the facts in front of them and come up with original solutions to challenges if they are to succeed outside of the classroom. Educators have tools at their disposal to help students learn this all-important skill, but education technology might be able to play a vital role. The appropriate educational technology initiatives and strategies can significantly advance fields related to critical thinking (Lynch, 2021).

Table 9. Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Pedagogical Indicators (Standard 1)

<i>Standard 1: Apply technology to develop students' higher order thinking skills and creativity</i>	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I can make students use databases, spreadsheets, concept mapping tools and communication tools, etc.	3.15	Neutral	Competent
I can encourage students to do data analysis, problem solving, decision making and exchange of ideas.	3.28	Neutral	Competent
Overall Mean	3.22	Neural	Competent

It is shown in Table 10 that the teachers thought of themselves as highly competent in the areas of using appropriate slide presentations, videos, audio, and other media in the classroom (3.64) and in teaching students to use various multimedia materials for the reports and class presentations (3.50).

Table 10. Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Pedagogical Indicators (Standard 2)

<i>Standard 2: Provide performance tasks that require students to locate and analyze information and use a variety of media clearly</i>	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I can use appropriately slide presentations, videos, audio and other media in the classroom.	3.64	Agree	Highly competent
I can teach students to use various multimedia materials for the reports and class presentations.	3.50	Agree	Highly competent
Overall Mean	3.57	Agree	Highly competent

The overall mean of 3.57 indicated that the teachers were perceived to be highly competent in providing performance tasks that required students to locate and analyze information and use a variety of media clearly.

For any teacher, measuring student learning is a crucial aspect of their job. To successfully prepare kids for college and the workforce, teachers must assess students' knowledge, and parents, students, and leaders must be aware of how well students are performing overall. Technology-enabled assessments can promote learning across subject areas and assist in minimizing the time, resources, and interruption to learning needed for the administration of paper exams (Gohl et al., 2009).

Table 11 presents the perceived level of competency of the teachers in terms of conducting open and flexible learning environments where technology is used to support a variety of interactions among students, cooperative learning, and peer instruction.

It is shown that the teachers perceived they were highly competent in terms of facilitating cooperative learning and exchange of ideas and information but only competent in terms of using various synchronous and asynchronous communication tools such as email, chat, whiteboards, forums, and blogs. Overall, the teachers perceived themselves as competent in this set of pedagogical indicators.

Learning always occurs in a context, and these days, that environment must be one that is technologically advanced (Lenhart, 2010). The most effective application of technology in education relates to a variety of tools and methods it offers since no single teaching method can meet the needs of various learners (Wilson & Smilanrich, 2005). Since education aims to prepare students for the world and the competitiveness of the workforce, new technology should be incorporated into the modern curriculum. An important consideration, however, is how to use technology so that it supports learning and teaching. Technology-supported learning may seem like an isolated activity, but to be used to the best benefit of the students, it should be turned into a collaborative task (Domalewska, 2014).

Table 11. Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Pedagogical Indicators (Standard 3)

<i>Standard 3: Conduct open and flexible learning environments where technology is used to support variety technology is used to support variety of interactions among students, cooperative learning and peer instruction</i>	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I can facilitate cooperative learning and exchange of ideas and information.	3.52	Agree	Highly competent
I can use various synchronous and asynchronous communication tools (email, chat, whiteboards, forum, and blogs).	3.40	Neutral	Competent
Overall Mean	3.46	Neutral	Competent

Table 12 shows that the teachers perceived themselves as competent in identifying educational sites and portals suitable to the subject area (3.49), joining online communities, subscribing to relevant mailing lists and online journals (3.41), reviewing new and existing software for education (3.23), and in recommending useful and credible websites to colleagues (3.23).

The overall mean of 3.34 indicated that the teachers were perceived as competent in proactively engaging in exploring and learning new and emerging technologies.

Kunnen (2015) emphasized that it is important to provide dedicated space to engage faculty and students with emerging educational technologies while encouraging their exploration of the possibilities that bring about new opportunities in teaching and learning. Furthermore, teachers should be intentional and innovative in the design of informal learning spaces that capture attention and promote awareness of new ideas, empowering faculty and students. Finally, tracking and exploring new technologies while monitoring trends in teaching practices helps a campus respond to faculty needs in teaching and students' desires for the optimal learning experience.

Table 12. Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Professional Competency (Standard 1)

<i>Standard 1: Proactively engage in exploring and learning new and emerging technologies</i>	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I can identify educational sites and portals suitable to the subject area.	3.49	Agree	Highly Competent
I can join online communities, subscribe to relevant mailing lists and online journals.	3.41	Agree	Highly Competent
I can review new and existing software for education.	3.23	Neutral	Competent
I can recommend useful and credible websites to colleagues.	3.23	Neutral	Competent
Overall Mean	3.34	Neutral	Competent

Table 13 shows that per the assessment of the teachers, they were competent in conducting research on the use of technology in the classroom (3.27), in following online tutorials or online degree programs (3.35), and in actively participating in online forums and discussions (3.38).

An overall mean of 3.33 indicated that the teachers were perceived as competent, continuously evaluating and reflecting on the use of technology in the professional indicators.

Technology is a tool to increase production and instruction; thus, its integration into a school is similar to that of any commercial environment in many aspects. Effectiveness must be quantified, yet some of the most important benefits can be challenging to evaluate. Technology can increase worker productivity for administrative jobs by eliminating tedious parts of complicated processes or by enhancing system communication. Since it fosters project-based learning, supports the development of "higher order thinking," analysis, and problem-solving abilities, and helps to alter teacher-student interactions, technology integration in the classroom has the

ability to support crucial educational goals as well. However, the most crucial justification for assessing is the knowledge that the influence of technology on schools depends on how well it is integrated (NCES, 2021).

Table 13. Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Professional Competency (Standard 2)

<i>Standard 2: Continuously evaluate and reflect on the use of technology in the profession indicators</i>	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I can conduct research on the use of technology in the classroom.	3.27	Neutral	Competent
I can follow online tutorials or online degree programs.	3.35	Neutral	Competent
I can actively participate in online forums and discussions.	3.38	Neutral	Competent
Overall Mean	3.33	Neutral	Competent

Table 14 shows the perceived competency of the teachers in Standard 3 of Professional Competency.

It is shown that, per the teachers' perception, they were competent in publishing formal/informal research on the use of ICT in education (3.03) and in sharing lesson plans, worksheets, templates, and teaching materials through course websites (3.18).

An overall mean of 3.11 indicated they perceived themselves as sufficiently competent in sharing experiences and expertise and collaborating with peers and stakeholders in advancing the use of technology in education and beyond.

Education innovations and the educational system are both seen as parts of a larger social super system that demonstrates their interdependencies at all levels. Raising the standard and scope of educational innovations will have a beneficial ripple effect that will benefit society as a whole (Serdyukov, 2017).

Table 14. Level of Competency of the Teachers in Terms of Professional Competency (Standard 3)

<i>Standard 3: Share experiences and expertise, and collaborate with peers and stakeholders in advancing the use of technology in education and beyond</i>	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I can publish (formal/informal) research on the use of ICT in education.	3.03	Neutral	Competent
I can share lesson plans, worksheets, templates and teaching materials through course websites.	3.18	Neutral	Competent
Overall Mean	3.11	Neutral	Competent

Table 15 summarizes the competencies of teachers in information and communications technology in Katangawan District Schools. It is shown that the perceived overall ICT competency of the teachers in Katangawan District Schools was at a neutral level and that the teachers were competent enough when it came to information and communications technology. The respondents were perceived to be very competent, most especially in the area of social and ethical standards but were only competent in the area of professional competency.

This implied that all the teachers in the aforementioned district must undergo seminars aimed at enhancing their competency level in computerization program with an emphasis on the following areas: (1) technology operation and concepts, (2) social and ethical, (3) pedagogical indicators, and (4) professional competency.

Table 15. ICT Competencies of Teachers in Katangawan District Schools

<i>Areas of ICT Competency</i>	Mean	Description
Technology Operations and Concepts	3.41	Highly competent
Social and Ethical Standards	3.45	Highly competent
Pedagogical Indicators	3.42	Highly competent
Professional Competency	3.26	Competent
Overall Mean	3.39	Competent

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, it is concluded that the teachers of the different schools in Katangawan District Schools perceived themselves to be moderately but sufficiently ICT competent.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are at this moment given:

Enhancing the knowledge and skills of millennial teachers in line with the DepEd computerization program is of utmost importance, considering their proficiency in technology. This entails sending more teachers to ICT-focused training and workshops, enabling them to update their technical expertise and share newfound knowledge with their colleagues, especially those who may be facing challenges in utilizing technology.

To fully leverage the potential of computer facilities in schools within the Katangawan District, it is crucial that they are appropriately utilized. Additionally, the local board can play a pivotal role by providing upgraded computer technology and software to DepEd schools, ensuring that teachers are eqped to meet the demands of modern teaching practices.

Periodic seminars focused on professional competency standards should be conducted to address areas identified by respondent

teachers as needing improvement. Teachers who have undergone training workshops and participated in ICT congress events can facilitate these seminars in-house.

While this study relied on perceptions, the author recommends future research that incorporates competency assessments based on scientific standards and compares the results with those obtained from this perception-based study. Furthermore, a comparative analysis of perceived or tested ICT competencies among teachers in urban and rural districts could offer valuable insights for further exploration.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Rossana L. Salanio

Department of Education – Philippines

Geraldine D. Rodriguez, EdD

Department of Education – Philippines